

**metaumbrella: free (graphical) tools to easily perform data analysis
in umbrella reviews with stratification of the evidence**

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https://corentinjosling.github.io/EBMH_2022_METAUMBRELLA/

Abstract

Objective. Umbrella reviews are a new form of literature review that summarizes the strength and/or quality of the evidence from all systematic reviews and meta-analyses conducted on a broad topic. This type of review thus provides an exhaustive examination of a vast body of information, providing the highest synthesis of knowledge. A critical strength of umbrella reviews is recalculating the meta-analytic estimates within a uniform framework to allow a consistent evidence stratification. To our best knowledge, there is no comprehensive package or software to conduct umbrella reviews.

Methods. The R package *metaumbrella* accomplishes this aim by building on three core functions that: (i) automatically perform all required calculations in an umbrella review (including but not limited to pairwise meta-analyses), (ii) stratify evidence according to various classification criteria, and (iii) generate a visual representation of the results. In addition, this package allows flexible inputs for each review or meta-analysis analyzed (e.g., means plus standard deviations, or effect size estimate and confidence interval) and customization (e.g., stratification criteria following Ioannidis, algorithmic-GRADE, or personalized classification).

Results. The R package *metaumbrella* thus provides the first comprehensive range of facilities to perform umbrella reviews with stratification of the evidence.

Conclusion. To facilitate the use of this package, even for researchers unfamiliar with R, we also provide a JAMOFI module and an open-access browser-based graphical interface that allow using the core functions of the package with a few mouse clicks.

Keywords: evidence, umbrella review, overview of reviews, meta-review, meta-analysis, R, JAMOFI, shiny

Systematic reviews and meta-analyses traditionally have been among the highest levels of evidence synthesis.[1] However, the number of systematic reviews and meta-analyses has gradually increased in recent decades to the point of becoming overwhelming in some fields.[2,3] Moreover, some meta-analyses overlap but come to different conclusions.[4] Umbrella reviews (sometimes called ‘overview of systematic reviews’, ‘overview’, ‘review of reviews’, etc.) are a new type of meta-evidence synthesis that has emerged in recent years to provide a bird’s eye summary on a wide body of evidence on a determinate topic.[5,6] To overcome inconsistencies in overlapping meta-analyses, authors of umbrella reviews commonly use different strategies. For example, to limit biases caused by the non-identification of studies, they may pool all the primary studies included in the overlapping meta-analyses or present the results of the meta-analysis with the largest number of studies. Alternatively, they may present the results of the meta-analysis with the highest methodological quality to direct readers to the current best evidence.[7-10] Thus, umbrella reviews provide a single document that synthesizes an extensive body of information that could not be generated within a single publication for feasibility reasons. For example, Radua and colleagues synthesized 55 meta-analytic papers that examined the effects of 170 putative risk and protective factors for psychotic disorders, based on 683 individual studies.[8] Clinical decision-makers may use the results of this umbrella review to access the main results that are relevant to a specific question.[9]

Umbrella reviews originated more than one decade ago and their number has grown exponentially ever since (peaking to more than 300 new umbrella reviews published in 2020).[6, 15, 16] However, even if conducting an umbrella review typically requires recalculating meta-analyses and performing extra calculations, no R package or other software has yet been specifically developed for data analysis in umbrella reviews. Numerous R packages such as meta, metafor, robumeta, metansue, dmetar, commercial software such as

Comprehensive Meta-analysis, SPSS, or STATA, and free software such as JAMOVI, allow performing meta-analyses [17-21]. Analyzing the data generated by an umbrella review with these tools is not straightforward for several reasons. First, authors of umbrella reviews must sequentially harmonize the input data. For a given effect size measure (e.g., Odds Ratio, OR), meta-analyses can report many different information (e.g., the contingency table *versus* the OR value and standard error *versus* the OR value and confidence interval). Second, authors have to manually convert the pooled effect sizes into the same metric to facilitate interpretation. Third, they have to conduct some additional calculations (e.g., a test of excess statistical significance or small-study effects). Fourth, because meta-analyses often have a complex data structure (such as non-independence between effect sizes), authors must build specific models for these situations.[26] Last, to stratify the evidence during an umbrella review, authors must manually extract information from the results. All these steps make conducting an umbrella review very time-consuming and, more critically, increases the risk of human errors, much especially when the number of meta-analyses included in the review is high. Researchers would thus largely benefit from a comprehensive suite for conducting umbrella reviews which can be customized to their needs.

The objective of this paper is to present an overview of the metaumbrella tools, which are designed to assist in data analysis during an umbrella review. In the following sections, we present the use of the R package metaumbrella to analyze the data generated by an umbrella review that contains meta-analyses with dependent effect sizes. We also present complete tutorials for conducting the same data analysis but using two graphical-user interface (GUI) platforms: a JAMOVI module and a browser-based application (<https://metaumbrella.org/>). These tutorials on the JAMOVI module and the browser-based app are available in Supplements 1 and 2, respectively.

Methods

To achieve automation in the calculations, the metaumbrella package (as well its companion JAMOVI module and browser-based app) requests that users build a dataset that follows fixed rules¹. Therefore, to guide users in this formatting, the package also proposes a function that specifically checks the formatting of the dataset and provides guidance on formatting issues detected (Fig. 1). Note that details on calculations conducted by the R package metaumbrella can be found in a dedicated vignette (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/metaumbrella/vignettes/calculations-details.html>).

First steps with the metaumbrella package

To use the metaumbrella package in R, it must first be *installed* (required only once, before the first use) and *loaded* (required each time R or R studio is opened) using the following respective commands

- `install.packages("metaumbrella")`
- `library(metaumbrella)`

Once these R commands have been run, all functions of the package and several example datasets become available. In this paper, we will use one of these datasets that is stored under the name `df.radua2019`. This dataset is directly inspired from an umbrella review conducted by Tortella-Feliu and colleagues and contains information on the putative risk factors for posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) collected from 155 studies and synthesized in seven meta-analyses.[27]

The following R command allows to visually explore this dataset

- `View(df.radua2019)`

¹ A detailed description of how building such a well-formatted dataset is beyond the scope of this paper, but readers may find a complete description in Supplement 3. In addition, a step-by-step tutorial with a concrete example is provided as a vignette of the package (<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/metaumbrella/vignettes/format-dataset.html>).

-- Figure 1 about here --

Check dataset formatting

The *view.errors.umbrella()* function has been specifically designed to guide users in the formatting of their dataset. By default, this function allows to obtain information on formatting problems of their dataset by (i) adding two columns to the original dataset (*column_type_errors* and *column_errors*) describing formatting issues encountered in each row of the dataset and (ii) generating messages listing all the formatting issues encountered.

Two types of formatting issues are identified. Formatting errors (such as negative sample sizes or standard errors, too little information to run the analyses, etc. . .) are issues that prevent running calculations. Formatting errors are associated, for each problematic row, with an "ERROR" value in the *column_type_errors* column and a description of the problem encountered in the *column_errors* column. In contrast, formatting warnings (such as non-symmetric confidence interval around the effect size, empty rows, etc.) are potential inconsistencies that do not prevent running calculations but that should be carefully reviewed by users before relying on the results generated by the metaumbrella package. Formatting warnings are associated, for each suspicious row, with a "WARNING" value in the *column_type_errors* column and with a description of the problem encountered in the *column_errors* column.

To use this function, it only requires to apply it on a dataframe

➤ *view.errors.umbrella(x = df.radua2019)*

In the JAMOVI module and in the browser-based app, this function is automatically run.

Conduct main calculations

To replicate the pairwise meta-analyses and to run additional calculations needed to stratify evidence in an umbrella review, the metaumbrella package relies on the *umbrella()* function.

This function performs :

- fixed-effect or random-effects meta-analyses
- tests for small-study effects
- tests for excess statistical significance
- jackknife leave-one-out analysis

The advantage of this function over standard R packages only designed for fitting a single meta-analysis lies in the possibility of (i) automatically fitting several pairwise meta-analyses when input information differs (e.g., eight different combinations of input information are possible to conduct an umbrella review with the odds ratio as effect size measure; Supplement 3); (ii) automatically extracting the necessary information to stratify the evidence ; (iii) automatically convert all pooled effect sizes in common metrics (standardized mean difference, mean difference, [log] risk ratio, [log] incident rate ratio, [log] hazard ratio, correlation and Fisher's z are automatically converted into equivalent Hedges' g [eG] and equivalent odds ratio [eOR]); (iv) automatically conduct additional calculations such as small-study effects and excess for statistical significance and (v) automatically handling multivariate situations where the same study reports multiple effect sizes (due to the presence of multiple outcomes measured in the same participants or due to the presence of multiple independent subgroups). In these multivariate situations, the *umbrella()* function automatically aggregates all the effect sizes coming from the same studies using the procedures described by Borenstein and colleagues.[28]

To use this function, it only requires applying it on a well-formatted dataset

➤ *umbrella(x = df.radua2019, mult.level = TRUE)*

The ‘mult.level’ argument should be set as ‘TRUE’ if the dataset contains at least one meta-analysis with a complex data structure, namely, with a dependence between some effect sizes (otherwise, this argument can be discarded). Several customizations are possible (such as the choice of the estimator of the between-study variance, the test of excess statistical significance, etc.). All possible customizations of the umbrella function can be obtained using the following command in R

➤ *help(umbrella)*

In the JAMOVI module and in the app, this function is automatically and can be customized to match the needs of the users.

Stratify the evidence

The *add.evidence()* function is used to algorithmically stratify evidence using the results of the calculations performed by the *umbrella()* function. Two pre-established criteria are proposed but users can also use some personalized criteria to adapt to the requirements of their umbrella review.

The first pre-established criteria are those proposed by Prof Ioannidis (Fusar-Poli and Radua 2018). These criteria propose to stratify evidence in five ordinal classes: "Class I", "Class II", "Class III", "Class IV", "Class ns", the "Class I" being the highest class that can be reached. The criteria for each class are available in Supplement 4.

The second pre-established criteria are inspired by the GRADE classification.[10, 11] Importantly, this algorithmic approach should not be taken as an equivalent to the approach underlying the standard GRADE criteria. However, in line with the standard GRADE approach, the GRADE classification used in the metaumbrella package stratifies evidence according to four ordinal classes ("High", "Moderate", "Low", "Very low") and uses a downgrading procedure. All factors start with a "High" evidence class that could then be

downgraded depending on four indicators. The criteria used to downgrade evidence are available in Supplement 4.

Last, because the criteria used to stratify evidence can vary depending on the aim of the umbrella review, the *add.evidence()* function offers the possibility to select the criteria used to stratify evidence as well as the cut-off values to reach each class. Similarly to the "Ioannidis" criteria, evidence is stratified in 5 ordinal classes, from "Class I" to "Class V" (the "Class I" being the highest class that can be reached). A total of 13 criteria can be used to stratify evidence: (1) the number of studies included in the meta-analysis, (2) the total number of participants included in the meta-analysis, (3) the number of cases included in the meta-analysis, (4) the p-value of the pooled effect size, (5) the inconsistency between individual studies (I^2 statistics), (6) the imprecision of the pooled effect size (the statistical power of the meta-analysis to detect a given SMD), (7) the percentage of participants included in studies at low risk of bias, (8) the methodological quality of the systematic review (AMSTAR score), (9) the p-value at the Egger's test for small-study effects,[29] (10) the p-value of the test of excess statistical significance,[30] (11) the highest p-value obtained in the Jackknife meta-analysis, (12) the inclusion of the null value in the 95% prediction interval and (13) the statistical significance of the largest study (i.e., with the smallest variance) included in the meta-analysis. Users can select any of the 13 criteria (minimum 1 and maximum 13) and must set the threshold scores for each selected criteria to reach the 5 possible classes.

The *add.evidence()* function requires two core arguments, the object in which the calculations performed by the *umbrella()* function are stored and the name of the criteria used to stratify evidence ("Ioannidis", "GRADE" or "Personalized"). Assuming that the calculations conducted by the *umbrella()* function have been stored in the object 'umb', the following R command allows to stratify the evidence according to the Ioannidis criteria

➤ *add.evidence(x = umb, criteria = "Ioannidis")*

All customizations for the personalized criteria can be obtained using the following command in R

➤ *help(add.evidence)*

In the JAMOVI module and in the app, this function is automatically and can be customized to match the needs of the users.

Generate a forest plot

A graphical presentation of the results can be obtained with the *forest()* function, which generates either a forest plot depicting the pooled effect sizes of the meta-analysis (if applied on an object generated by *umbrella()* function) or a forest plot along with information on the stratification of evidence (if applied on an object generated by the *add.evidence()* function).

By default, the size of the dot of each pooled effect size is depicted proportionally to the precision of the estimate. Assuming that the results of the stratification of the evidence have been stored in the object 'strat', the following R command allows to produce a forest plot along with information on the stratification of evidence.

➤ *forest(x = strat)*

The *forest()* function contains many arguments to control the output of the plot (such as the titles of the plot and axis, the color and size of the dots and text, etc.). A complete description of all arguments can be obtained using the following R command

➤ *help(forest.umbrella)*

In the JAMOVI module and in the app, this function is automatically and can be customized to match the needs of the users.

Results

In this section we will present the main results generated by the four functions presented in the previous section. Note that the functions of the metaumbrella package automatically present the results converted into two effect size measures, equivalent Hedges' g (eG) or equivalent Odds Ratio (eOR). By parsimony, we present here the results only in eG.

Checking of the dataset formatting

As can be seen in Fig.2., the `view.errors.umbrella()` returns only a message explaining that the dataset is correctly formatted since no errors were detected. If errors had been detected, the function would have returned a message displaying all errors encountered, as well as a dataset containing only the rows of the original dataset with formatting issues.

In the JAMOVI module and in the browser-based app, results of this function can be easily accessed (see part B of Fig. 3 and Fig. 4).

Main calculations

General information on the meta-analyses. The `umbrella()` function returns a dataset in which each meta-analysis (identified in the 'Factor' column), has its results described in its own row (therefore, each row is independent of the others). The number of studies ('n_studies'), the total number of participants ('total_n'), the number of cases ('n_cases') and the number controls ('n_controls') included in the meta-analyses are presented.

Meta-analytic results. Users are presented with the type of effect size measure used in the calculations ('measure'), the pooled effect sizes ('value'), their 95% CIs ('value_CI'), and their p-values ('p_value'). Information on the I^2 statistics for inconsistency ('I2') and on the 95% prediction interval (PI) is also available. Since different factors may use different effect size measures, the `umbrella()` function automatically converts the pooled effect sizes and their

95% CI as well as the 95% PI into eG and eOR (respectively, 'eG' and 'eOR', 'eG_CI' and 'eOR_CI', 'PI_eG' and 'PI_eOR').

Additional calculations. Regarding small-study effects, the function performs an Egger's test for small-study effects (the associated p-value is available in the Egger_p column) and estimates whether the 95% CI of the largest study includes the null value ('largest_eG_CI' and 'largest_eOR_CI' columns). Regarding excess of significance bias, the p-value of the test is available in the 'ESB_p' column. Moreover, the largest p-value obtained in the Jackknife leave-one-out analysis is reported in the 'JK_p' column. Last, the *umbrella()* function also estimates the statistical power to detect a SMD of 0.5 at an alpha of 5% based on the total number of cases and controls included in the meta-analysis (the estimated power is available in the 'power_med' column). Note that in the case of IRR, the number of cases and controls for this calculation are equal to half the number of cases included in the meta-analysis. In the case of R and Z, the number of cases and controls for this calculation is equal to half the total sample size. This analysis gives an indication on whether the number of cases and controls included in the meta-analysis gives sufficient statistical power to a single study to detect a moderate effect size.

In the JAMOVI module and in the browser-based app, results of this function are presented in the main page (see part D of Fig. 3 and Fig. 4).

Stratification of the evidence

In this example, we used personalized criteria to stratify the evidence. Note that these criteria are used for illustrative purposes and are not intended to be guidelines on the criteria that should be applied in an umbrella review. As can be seen in Fig.2, we requested that:

1. a class I can be achieved if the total number of studies is strictly larger than 30, the p-value of the meta-analysis is strictly lower than 0.005, the inconsistency is strictly

- lower than 50%, the Egger's test for small-study effects is not significant ($p > .05$) and the maximum p-value achieved in the jackknife meta-analysis remains statistically significant ($p < .05$).
2. a class II can be achieved if the total number of studies is strictly larger than 20, the p-value of the meta-analysis is strictly lower than 0.005, the Egger's test for small-study effects is not significant ($p > .05$) and the maximum p-value achieved in the jackknife meta-analysis remains statistically significant ($p < .05$).
 3. a class III can be achieved if the total number of studies is strictly larger than 15, the p-value of the meta-analysis is strictly lower than 0.01, and the Egger's test for small-study effects is not significant ($p > .05$).
 4. a class IV can be achieved if the p-value of the meta-analysis is strictly lower than 0.05.
 5. a class V is automatically assigned if criteria for classes I-IV are not met.

In the JAMOVI module and in the browser-based app, results of this function are presented in the same table of the results of the `umbrella()` function (see part D of Fig. 3 and Fig. 4).

Graphical presentation of the results

Once the calculations needed for an umbrella review and the stratification of the evidence are completed, users can obtain a graphic presentation of the results using the `forest()` function. Users can easily improve the basic figure by using the arguments of the `forest()` function. For this example, we generate a forest plot that contains information on the stratification of evidence (according to the Personalized classification), and in which two columns and a title for the plot have been added. The entire code for generating such an enhanced plot is available in Supplement 5.

In the JAMOVI module and in the browser-based app, a forest plot can be generated (see part E of Fig. 3 and Fig. 4).

-- Figures 2, 3 and 4 about here --

Discussion

Umbrella reviews are a new type of evidence synthesis that summarizes and stratifies the quality or strength of the evidence from all systematic reviews and meta-analyses conducted on a broad topic. The metaumbrella tools presented in this manuscript are the first tools dedicated to data analysis in umbrella reviews with stratification of the evidence. In addition to the R package – which requires the mastering a programming language – we have developed two open-access GUI-based platforms: a JAMOVI module and a browser-based application (<https://metaumbrella.org/>). These two platforms allow to use the functions of the R metaumbrella package with a few mouse clicks, and thus facilitate the completion of umbrella reviews to a large community.

There are currently no methods or criteria that can be applied to all umbrella reviews to stratify the evidence. Consequently, an important focus in the development of our tools has been to offer a wide range of customizations to adapt to user needs. Users are provided with 13 personalized criteria for stratifying the evidence, some of which are based on the results of statistical analyses (e.g., presence of small-study effects) while others are based on information reported by users (e.g., methodological quality of primary studies).

As umbrella reviews are a relatively new approach compared to systematic reviews or meta-analyses, many developments are still ongoing. For example, a growing number of umbrella reviews focus on meta-analyses of prevalence or include network-meta-analyses. In addition, new tools, such as GROOVE tables to identify the overlap of primary studies

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between studies, are emerging. These features – currently not available in metaumbrella tools – constitute avenues for improvement in the future

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Figure captions

Figure 1. Description of the main functions of the metaumbrella package

Figure 2. R commands (in blue) and outputs generated by the functions of the metaumbrella package.

Figure 3. Illustration of the JAMОВI module. (A) Loading of the dataset. (B) Dataset formatting checks. (C) Customizations for the meta-analytic models, test for excess of significance, criteria for stratification of the evidence and forest plot. (D) Results of the meta-analyses and of the stratification of the evidence. (E) Forest plot.

Figure 4. Illustration of the browser-based application. (A) Loading of the dataset. (B) Dataset formatting checks. (C) Customizations of the meta-analytic models, test for excess of significance and criteria for stratification of the evidence. (D) Results of the meta-analyses and of the stratification of the evidence. (E) Forest plot.